

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D2.3 - Data fields for ET harmonisation

Authors:

Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE), Jordi CIPRIANO (CIMNE), Stoyan DANOV (CIMNE), Gerard MOR (CIMNE)

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Authors	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE), Jordi CIPRIANO (CIMNE), Stoyan DANOV (CIMNE), Gerard MOR (CIMNE)
Contributors	Xavier PALOMÉ (DDGI), Georgia PILIGOTSI (RDFC), Tomáš PERUTKA (EAZK)

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document presents a quick overview of the identified Use Cases in each of the three pilot sites: Zlín region (Czech Republic), Crete island (Greece) and Girona province (Spain). With the pilots are described the data sources and their linking points explaining how this data will be uploaded and harmonised to the ePLANET platform.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
API	Application Programming Interface
BEI	Baseline Emissions Inventory
CD	Compact Disc
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
COM	Covenant of Mayor
COMO	Covenant of Mayor Office
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
DATADIS	Web platform where the major Spanish DSO offer the electricity consumption data of the electricity clients: https://datadis.es/en/home
DDGI	Council of Girona
DSO	Distribution System Operator
ET	Energy Transition
ETM	Energy Transition Measures
EU ETS	EU Emissions Trading System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Green House Gases
GIS	Geographic Information System
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estadística (https://ine.es/en/index.htm)
PAES	Sustainable energy action plan
PAESC	Sustainable energy action and climate plan
POUM	Municipal Urban Planning Plan

PV	Photovoltaics
LAU	Local Administrative Units
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
NUT	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
R2RML	RDB to RDF Mapping Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RES	Renewable energy System
RML	RDF Mapping Language
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
WWTP	Waste-Water Treatment Plant
.csv	Format of a simplified version of an excel file
.json	JavaScript Object Notation. A language-independent data format
UC#	Use Case

1 Introduction to the ePLANET project

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action co-founded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims to deploy **new clustering governance** for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

The development of ePLANET aims at deploying Energy Transition (ET) in the public sector. The main challenges are:

- Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments,
- Enhancing the decision-making process in the deployment of ET projects,
- Providing coherence and consistency to the energy transition measures (ETM) to be implemented,
- Encouraging the digitalisation of measures and plans,
- Enabling an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools.

All these targeted objectives will support the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

This document summarises the actions performed and the conclusions obtained to define the basis for harmonising the information regarding ET measures, actions and plans. The deliverable starts with a review of the content and data formats of existing classification structures and templates based on previous actions and the most relevant plans (SEAPs/SECAPs for CoM signatories) in the case of Greece and Spain, and the Green City Action Plans for green and healthy cities initiatives in the Czech Republic. It follows the definition of the ePLANET data fields for each specific use case in each pilot site. The deliverable finishes with a cross-reference of the outcomes of each use case with the EU Taxonomy data model.

2 Description of pilot regions and identified use-cases

The three pilot regions of ePLANET project are: Zlín Region (Czech Republic), Crete Island (Greece) and Girona province (Spain). Although there is a common strategy, each pilot region has its specificities and local needs, summarised in several use cases.

Figure 2-1 Map of the ePLANET pilot site regions (Girona, Zlín Region and Crete)

In deliverable D.2.1, a first identification of the use cases to be developed within ePLANET project was performed. A summary of them is shown in the following table:

Table 2-1 Summary of use cases in each pilot region

UC#	Description		ZLÍN REGION	CRETE	GIRONA REGION
UC1	Digitalization of SECAP drafting and monitoring process	Scope	---	To improve the update and monitoring of SECAPs through advanced web-based environments	To improve the update and monitoring of SECAPs through advanced web-based environments
		n° of municipalities	---	16 which already signed the SECAP agreement	20 landscape units + 67 municipalities

UC#	Description		ZLÍN REGION	CRETE	GIRONA REGION
		Data format	---	PDF of the submitted SEAP. To be transferred to the new SECAP excel file of COM platform	Excel files of the SECAPs provided by the consultancy companies
UC2	Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock	Scope	To implement a system to track and assess the energy consumption of public buildings belonging to several municipalities and the Zlín region	To implement a system to track and evaluate the energy consumption of public buildings belonging to several municipalities and the regional administration of Crete	---
		n° of municipalities /buildings	70-80 public buildings of 61 Zlín region municipalities 300 public buildings belonging to the regional administration of Zlín Region	<u>First stage:</u> public buildings of 4 municipalities <u>Second stage:</u> public buildings of 16 municipalities added to public buildings of the regional government of Crete	---
		Data format	Excel files including the monthly energy consumption of the buildings and their geographical coordinates.	.xls files of monthly electricity consumption for the last five years	---

UC#	Description		ZLÍN REGION	CRETE	GIRONA REGION
UC3	Geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities (REC & CEC)	Scope	Showcase of the city of Hostětin as a sustainable energy community	Geographically based web visualisations of building energy consumption and renewable energy generation aggregated at municipality level	Creation of a geo referenced visualisation tool to support the planning of local energy communities (PV and biomass as RES) and the energy transition of the building sector
		n° of municipalities	1	<p><u>First stage:</u> public buildings of 4 municipalities¹</p> <p><u>Second stage:</u> public buildings of 16 municipalities added to public buildings of the regional government of Crete</p>	<p><u>First stage:</u> 6 municipalities²</p> <p><u>Second stage:</u> 67 municipalities</p>
		Data format	Pending confirm detailed data needs with a detailed email after the project meeting ends*	<p>Data on RES installations in xls format (since 2019; power and location)</p> <p>Electricity consumption of 24 municipalities, split by sector (residence, Public lighting, public buildings, water management,</p>	<p>.csv files sent by the gas and electricity DSO</p> <p>Json files from the public API of DATADIS</p> <p>Geo referenced files from the Spanish cadaster web portal</p> <p>Weather data from weather</p>

¹ Ag. Nikolaos, Hersonissos, Rethymno, Chania

² Campdevanol, Cassa de la Selva, Palafrugell, Ripoll, Sant Feliu de Guixols, Sarria del Ter

UC#	Description		ZLÍN REGION	CRETE	GIRONA REGION
				agriculture, trade and industry)	forecasting services Solar potential studies or solar potential maps Potential of biomass boilers
UC4	PV potential analysis for public buildings	Scope	To set up a GIS based web environment to show the PV potential and the self-consumption ratio of the public buildings of Zlín Region	---	---
		n° of municipalities /buildings	70-80 rooftops belonging to the public buildings of the 61 municipalities	---	---
		Data format	LIDAR data available in the CDs. Cadastral information of Zlín Region from: https://data.europa.eu	---	---

3 Data harmonisation to a unique data model

The data harmonisation layer aims to unify different data sources into a unique database. This process makes the data from diverse databases comparable by linking the various fields of a database into a standardised data model.

In ePLANET, although each use case has its specifications, they can be grouped in common concepts. The data harmonisation process will help all the heterogeneous data sources to be integrated into the ePLANET data model. A detailed description of this data model will be included in deliverable D3.1. This document, the deliverable D2.3, will only provide basic information about the data model.

3.1 Digitalization of SECAP drafting and monitoring process (UC1)

This use case corresponds with the UC1 of Table 2-1. It will be implemented in the pilot sites of Crete Island and the Girona province. This use case's main scope consists of developing the necessary web-based environment to support both public authorities, DDGI and RDFC, to perform the following up of the SECAPs. In addition, it will support dynamic monitoring of the GHG inventory, the committed Energy Transition Measures and the actions committed within the climate action plan.

The Covenant of Mayor signatories aims to reduce their CO₂ emissions by more than 40 % by 2030, through energy efficiency and renewable energy. Within this agreement, local authorities commit:

- To prepare a Baseline Emission Inventory (BEI) as a compilation of baseline data.
- To present a SECAP, approved by the full council of the municipality, no later than two years from the date of formal accession to the new Covenant, and outline the measures and policies they intend to implement to achieve the objectives.
- To regularly prepare, after the publication of the SECAP, implementation reports indicating the degree of implementation of the programme (every two years) and action reports with interim results (every four years). The latter reports will include the Monitoring Emission Inventory (MEI).

This use case addresses explicitly the last commit, the reporting about the degree of implementation of the programme.

3.1.1 Methodology for the following up of SECAPs

Girona Provincial Council has been the territorial coordinator of the Covenant of Mayors since January 2012. The Regional Development Fund of Crete is not the coordinator of the COM in Crete, however, it acts as a supervisor of their implementation. They have the following functions:

- Articulation and leadership of the programme: structuring and mentoring of the support structure.
- Contact the European Commission and COMO.
- Administrative, legal and technical support in the different processes and initiatives.
- Preparation of essential documentation (methodologies, procedures, forms, etc.).
- Channelling and managing sources of funding.
- Identification of feasible short-term actions of current initiatives and adaptation to the Covenant of Mayors programme.

- Promotion of new initiatives in the framework of the Covenant of Mayors.
- Contracting assistance for the preparation of technical documentation.
- Validation of the SECAP of the municipalities of the counties of Girona.
- Financial support to local councils for the drafting and implementing the SECAPs.

The main phases of a SECAP implementation and following up are summarized in the table below:

Table 3-1 Summary of the SECAP implementation process

PHASE	STAGE	DELIVERABLES	REF. DOCUMENT	DEADLINE
Initial Phase	Political commitment and signing of the SECAP	plenary agreement membership form	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposed model of plenary session agreement, • Text of COM, • Membership form, • Questions and answers for municipalities. 	
	Adaptation of municipal structures			
	Definition of the objective: municipal or by landscape unit			
Planning	Assessment of the present framework, including the BEI report	+ BEI of the city council + SECAP Template	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spreadsheet to request data, • BEI of the counties, • SECAP Template of each municipality, • SECAP reference document. 	In two years
	Vision setting: where do we want to go?	• SECAP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines for SECAP writing, • Vulnerability analysis form of each municipality, • Spreadsheet for data gathering of climate change vulnerability of each municipality, • Mitigation actions guidelines, • Adaptation to climate change guidelines, • Spreadsheet of a cost analysis of each mitigation action, • Plan for boosting RES. 	
	Plan development: how do we want to achieve it?			
	Approval and submission of the plan			

Implementation	Implementation	• SECAP	• Guidelines for SECAP writing	Every four years
Monitoring and information	Follow up	• SECAP review	• Guidelines for SECAPs writing	Every two years
	Reporting and submission of regular implementation and action reports		• Guidelines for the review reports of the committed actions	
	Review			

Following the stages defined in Table 3-1, the SECAP is finally structured in three main sections:

1. **CO₂ emissions inventory:** Which includes the BEI and the CO₂ emissions of the year when the SECAP is updated
2. **Action plan for mitigation:** Which includes all the mitigation actions committed by the municipalities to achieve the emissions reduction target
3. **Action plan for adaptation:** Which includes the most relevant information regarding the municipality's capacity to respond to climate change and the assessment of risks and vulnerabilities to climate change impacts.

Specificities of SECAP procedure in Girona region: Municipal and supra-municipal levels

The emission reduction target will be municipal, although in the event that the municipalities of the same landscape unit agree, the target can be supra municipal. This option is the one chosen by DDGI to implement the new updates of SECAPs in the Girona region. The following table shows the steps to follow for this option:

Table 3-2 Summary of steps to be followed in the supra-municipal approach

	Supra-municipal objective (Joint SECAP Option 2)
Target 40% emission reduction	<p>Global commitment</p> <p>The set of municipalities of the landscape unit commits to reduce by more than 40% the emissions from its entire territory.</p>
Preparation of the SECAP	<p>Supra-municipal SECAP</p> <p>The municipalities will jointly draw up the SECAP. This document shall include the results of the inventory of emissions benchmark for all municipalities (one BEI for all municipalities) and the whole of the SECAP actions to be taken by each group. In the event that actions are proposed for a single municipality, they shall contribute to adaptation to climate change and to the emissions reductions for the territory as a whole that includes the SECAP.</p> <p>The group must designate a person in charge of coordinating the elaboration of the SECAP and its implementation (this may be the territorial coordinator).</p>

Adoption of the SECAP	Each municipality will have to approve the SECAP by plenary agreement.
Processing of the SECAP	Municipalities will only have to submit the SECAP of the landscape unit and a single <i>SECAP_template</i> .

3.1.2 Common input data format file

In order to simplify the task of data collection and harmonization, the regional authorities (DDGI and RDFC) provide the city councils with a spreadsheet to be able to collect the data necessary for the preparation of the SECAP. Below is an outline of the contents of the spreadsheet for each of the sections of the SECAP and, in the case of Girona region, for both municipal and supra-municipal levels.

Input data for the Inventory of CO₂ emissions

The input data necessary to define the inventory of both the baseline year and the current year are summarized in the following table:

Table 3-3 Summary of the input data necessary for the inventory of CO₂ emissions

SECTOR	SCOPE	METHODOLOGY	SOURCE
BASIC DATA OF THE MUNICIPALITY			
Details of the municipality	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Date of the plenary agreement of the SECAP	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
SECAP documents	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND EMISSIONS IN BUILDINGS, EQUIPMENT/FACILITIES MUNICIPAL BUILDINGS AND EQUIPMENT			
Electricity	City Council	SECAP of landscape unit	City Council
Natural gas	City Council	SECAP of landscape unit	City Council
Diesel	City Council	SECAP of landscape unit	City Council
Liquefied gases	City Council	SECAP of landscape unit	City Council
Biomass	City Council	SECAP of landscape unit	City Council
Solar thermal energy	City Council	SECAP of landscape unit	City Council
Geothermal energy	City Council	SECAP of landscape unit	City Council
Buildings and equipment/facilities of the tertiary sector (non-municipal)			

Electricity	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Natural gas	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Liquefied gases	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Diesel	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Biomass	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Solar thermal energy	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	City Council
Geothermal energy	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	City Council
Residential buildings			
Electricity	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Natural gas	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Liquefied gases	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Diesel	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Biomass	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Solar thermal energy	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
Geothermal energy	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	BEI of Landscape unit
STREET LIGHTING			
Electricity	City Council	SECAP methodology	BEI of landscape unit
Industries not participating in the ETS13	City Council	SECAP methodology	BEI of landscape unit
Electricity	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	City Council
Natural gas	SECAP	BEI of landscape unit	City Council
ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND EMISSIONS IN TRANSPORT			
Urban road transport: municipal fleet			
Diesel oil	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Petrol	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Liquefied gases	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Natural gas	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Electricity	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Urban road transport: public transport			

Diesel oil	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Petrol	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Liquefied gases	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Natural gas	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Electricity	City Council	SECAP methodology	City Council
Urban road transport: private and commercial			
Petrol	City Council	SECAP methodology	BEI of landscape unit (CORAS14/DGT15)
Diesel	City Council	SECAP methodology	BEI of landscape unit (CORAS14/DGT15)
Electricity	City Council	SECAP methodology	BEI of landscape unit (CORAS14/DGT15)
LOCAL ENERGY PRODUCTION			
Fuel consumption for electricity production	SECAP	SECAP methodology	City Council
Fuel consumption for the production of heat/cold	SECAP	SECAP methodology	City Council
OTHER EMISSION SOURCES			
Waste management	SECAP	SECAP methodology	Agència de Residus de Catalunya

Each of the fields summarized in the previous table, include several input variables which are described more in detail below:

1. Basic data of the municipality

Table 3-4 Municipality basic input variables

INPUT VARIABLES
Details of the municipality and contact person
Date of the plenary agreement of the SECAP approval council
LAU 2 code
SECAP Documents to be attached (if applicable):
Final SECAP of the municipality and SECAP monitoring report
Mobility of the municipality
Mobility assessment study generated by the POUM

Plan for the adaptation of outdoor lighting / Lighting master plan / Inventory of lighting points Energy audits of public lighting
Energy audits of municipal buildings/facilities
Energy performance certificates for existing public buildings
Information on the use of biomass, biogas, heat networks, electric vehicle charging, etc.
Municipal by-laws on energy efficiency, water and climate change adopted
Others (climate change adaptation studies, energy budgets, projects for the legalisation of installations, etc.).

2. Consumption data for public buildings, facilities and installations

Table 3-5 Public buildings, facilities and installations consumption data input variables

INPUT VARIABLES
Name of building
Location (address)
Management: direct/indirect
Electricity consumption (kWh)
Year 2005
Current year
Cost of electricity (Euros)
Year 2005
Current year
Consumption for thermal uses
Year 2005
Current year
Energy source
Consumption units (tn, l, m ³ , kWh, etc.)
Fuel cost (Euros)
Year 2005
Current year
Energy production
Location
Energy source

Energy typology
Year of installation
Installed power (kW)
Self-consumption photovoltaic surplus energy compensation (yearly)(kWh)
Estimated occupancy
Months
Employment typology

3. Street lighting data

Table 3-6 Street lighting input variables

INPUT VARIABLES
Light box
Ignition system
Type of flow regulation
Type of luminaire
Typology of lamps
Number of light points
Installed power
Contracted power
Electricity consumption (kWh) for reference year (2005) and for current year
Cost of electricity (Euros) for reference year (2005) and for current year

4. Traffic lighting data

Table 3-7 Traffic lighting input variables

INPUT VARIABLES
Number of traffic lights
Typology
Electricity consumption (kWh) for reference year (2005) and for current year
Cost of electricity (Euros) for reference year (2005) and for current year

5. Municipal transport data

Table 3-8 Municipal transport input variables

INPUT VARIABLES
Municipally owned vehicle fleet
Brand and model
Fuel (petrol/diesel/electricity/LPG/natural gas/hydrogen/biogas)
Total Km
Year of registration
Consumption for the year 2005 and for the current year
Urban public transport
Brand and model
Fuel (petrol/diesel/electricity/LPG/natural gas/hydrogen/biogas)
Total Km
Year of registration
Average number of users
Consumption for the year 2005 and for the current year
Consumption associated with waste transport
Consumption for the year 2005 and for the current year within the municipality and to the final transfer plant (l/year)
Km associated with waste transport
Urban school transport
Brand and model
Fuel (petrol/diesel/electricity/LPG/natural gas/hydrogen/biogas)
Total Km
Year of registration
Average number of users
Consumption for the year 2005 and for the current year

An example of the excel file template which includes all these input fields is shown in Annex I: SECAP template.

Input data for the mitigation action plan

The action plan should identify and describe the actions that the municipality should take to achieve the target of reducing emissions by at least 40% of its territory. In order to structure the actions, they are divided into five strategic lines:

1. Increase the degree of energy savings and efficiency in public buildings and municipal facilities/equipment, residential buildings and those in the tertiary sector.
2. Reduce emissions associated with urban transport.
3. Increase local generation from renewable sources in the municipality.
4. To reduce emissions associated with the treatment of municipal solid waste.
5. Reducing emissions associated with Industries not participating in the EU ETS16.

Input data for each mitigation action

The proposed actions will have to be described in detail and, in the case of actions with a considerable investment by the municipality, it will be necessary to indicate the previous studies that will have to be carried out in order to specify the amount of the investment and the technical and economic viability. The set of actions will have to be synthesised by completing the table below. The fields indicated in the table below correspond to the fields to be filled in the Annex I: SECAP template.

Table 3-9 Input data of each climate change mitigation action

Action	Area of intervention	Political Instrument	Origin of action	Responsible	Starting date	End date	Cost (Euros)	Energy savings (MWh/year)	Energy generation (MWh/year)	CO ₂ emissions savings (tnCO ₂ /year)
MUNICIPAL BUILDINGS & FACILITIES										
NON-MUNICIPAL TERTIARY BUILDINGS & FACILITIES										
RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS										
INDUSTRY										

Action	Area of intervention	Political Instrument	Origin of action	Responsible	Starting date	End date	Cost (Euros)	Energy savings (MWh/year)	Energy generation (MWh/year)	CO ₂ emissions savings (tnCO ₂ /year)
TRANSPORT										
LOCAL ENERGY GENERATION										
LOCAL HEATING AND COOLING GENERATION										
OTHER										
WASTE										

Input data for the climate change adaptation plan

The SECAP's climate change adaptation plan indicates the most relevant information regarding the municipality's capacity to respond to climate change and the assessment of risks and vulnerabilities to climate change impacts. This section also indicates the consumption and use of water in the municipality, the drinking water supply infrastructures, the wastewater sanitation system and whether it has systems for using rainwater or water from the WWTP.

The input data necessary of the climate change adaptation plan are included as new tabs in the Annex I: SECAP template. A summary of them is shown in the following checklist tables:

1. Executive organisation of the municipality*Table 3-10 Adaptation plan; executive organisation of the municipality*

INPUT VARIABLES
Areas or cross-cutting commission on climate change adaptation in the city council
Areas or departments of the city council
PAESC Documents to be attached (if applicable):
Protocol for warning the population
Areas without mobile coverage in the municipality

2. Capacity to act and available resources*Table 3-11 Adaptation plan; action capacity and available resources*

INPUT VARIABLES
Buildings: municipal, residential and tertiary buildings
Transport
Energy
Water
Waste
Urban planning
Agriculture and forestry
Environment and diversity
Health
Protection and emergencies
Tourism
Public procurement of products and services
Other

3. Emergency services and civil protection

Table 3-12 Adaptation plan; emergency services and civil protection

INPUT VARIABLES
Municipal action plans
Level of associated risk
Municipal planning and services
Approval and date
Associations of civil protection volunteers in the municipality
Forest Defence Associations (ADF) in the municipality
Municipality's electrical installations critical in case of snowfall and storms

4. Heat and cold waves

Table 3-13 Adaptation plan; heat and cold waves

INPUT VARIABLES
Climate refuges in the municipality
Heat-sensitive infrastructure and other climatic phenomena
Shaded areas and water fountains in public spaces
Type of insulation in municipal facilities
Protocols for municipal action in the event of a heat wave
Energy self-sufficiency of the municipality

5. Droughts and water shortages

Table 3-14 Adaptation plan; droughts and water shortages

INPUT VARIABLES
Drinking water self-sufficiency
Guarantee of water supply in the municipality
Water restrictions in the municipality
Storage capacity of drinking water reservoirs in the municipality
Type of agriculture in the municipality (rainfed or irrigated)
Weight of livestock activity in the municipality
Area of urban green space in the municipality
Urban Green Master Plan

Priority to indigenous and/or low-water-use species
Urban irrigation system of the municipality
Available aquifers
Groundwater or alternative resource development plans
Monitoring or studies of leaks and losses in the supply network.
Percentage of losses, leaks and uncontrolled in the supply network
Water bill tariff system
Years of the last droughts in the municipality and their main consequences
Reuse of wastewater or reclaimed water from the WWTP
Rainwater harvesting systems or tanks
Municipal ordinance for the saving and reuse of water
Drinking water supply master plan

6. Fire risk

Table 3-15 Adaptation plan; fire risk

INPUT VARIABLES
Power lines crossing forest areas
Maintenance of power lines
Municipal road plan
Presence of campsites, holiday camps, rural tourism or housing estates in the municipality forest area
Tourist value of the natural landscape of the municipality

7. Extreme precipitation and flooding

Table 3-16 Adaptation plan; Extreme precipitation and flooding

INPUT VARIABLES
Rivers or torrents crossing the urban area that have caused flooding
River and torrential flood cones that may affect the urban area
Black spots in the municipality (bridges, fords, barriers or other infrastructures crossing watercourses)
Urban land affected by flood zone with a return period of 100 years
Sizing of the sewerage network
Separate rainwater and wastewater networks in the municipality

Sewerage master plan
Public facilities located in flood zones

8. Water management data

Table 3-17 Adaptation plan; water management data

INPUT VARIABLES
Municipal water supply management system (direct or outsourced management).
Details of the concessionary company, if any.
Municipal water consumption data
Volume invoiced (m ³ /year)
Total number of clients
Average water consumption per day (m ³ /day)
.....
Household endowment (litres/inhab. and day)
Register of municipal catchments (own sources)
Name of the well or catchment
Type of catchment (underground or surface)
.....
Problems encountered (quantity, quality, distance, etc.)
Volume of water according to its origin (own sources or purchase from upstream)
Volume of water purchased at discharge (m ³ /year)
Volume of water from own sources (m ³ /year)
Volume of water purchased at discharge (%)
Performance of the municipality's water supply network
Percentage of uncontrolled, leaks and losses by Municipality
Which installations have remote management systems?
If there is a municipal ordinance promoting water saving and reuse
Water supply at the scale of a town hall
State of the sewerage network and systems by core area
Waste water treatment plant in the municipality
Reclaimed water reuse systems (location, reclaimed water use, year of installation, volume of reclaimed water)

Rainwater harvesting and harvesting systems

Facilities with rainwater harvesting and rainwater harvesting systems

9. Input data for each climate change adaptation action

The proposed actions will have to be described in detail and, in the case of actions with a considerable investment by the municipality, it will be necessary to indicate the previous studies that will have to be carried out in order to specify the amount of the investment and the technical and economic viability. The set of actions will have to be synthesised by completing the table below. The fields indicated in the table below correspond to the fields to be filled in the Annex I: SECAP template.

Table 3-18 Input data of each climate change adaptation action

Sector	Climate impacts	Status	Origin of action	Description	Starting date	End date	Cost (Euros)	Maintenance cost (Euros)	Contributes to mitigation?	Key action?
Buildings	Extreme heat	Not started	Local authority							
Transportation	<u>Extreme cold</u>	Ongoing	National							
Energy	Extreme rainfall	Completed	regional							
Water	Floods	Cancelled								
Waste	Sea level rise									
Land Use Planning	Droughts									
Agriculture and forestry	Storms									
Environment and biodiversity	landslide									
Health	Forest fires									
Civil protection & emergencies	Transversal									
Tourism	Others									
Others										

3.1.3 Data harmonization process

Harmonization of the Inventory of CO₂ emissions data

The harmonization will consist in a manual mapping between the template of Annex I: SECAP template and the data model of the harmonization module of ePLANET. To facilitate this harmonization, the data model will follow the same structure as the inventory of emissions of the Annex I: SECAP template.

Harmonization of data for the mitigation action plan

The harmonization of the mitigation actions will consist in a manual mapping between the SECAP Template of the Annex I: SECAP template, and the data model of ePLANET. The ePLANET data model for this use case is organized in several linked tables within a non-structured database (Mongo DB). The templates of the tables corresponding to the actions for mitigation of climate change, are shown in the following tables:

Table 3-19 Template of the input table of mitigation action in ePLANET data model

Hierarchical level 1	Sectors	USE	Intervention area	Instrument	Source of action	Execution status
SECTOR	Municipal, residential and tertiary buildings, equipment / facilities	ALL	variable depending on sector	variable depending on sector	Local authority	Not started
	Public lighting				Territorial coordinator	In progress
	Industry				Others (national, regional, ...)	Completed
	Transportation					
	Local electricity generation					
	Local heating / cooling production					
	Others					

Table 3-20 Template of intervention areas table by sector

Intervention areas according to Sector						
EDI	ENL	IND	TRA	GEL	GCR	ALT
Equipment_buildings	Street_lighting	Industry	Transport	Local_electricity_production	Locally_generated_heating_and_cooling	Others
Building envelope	Energy efficiency	Energy efficiency in industrial processes	Low emissions/more efficient vehicles	Hydroelectric power	Cogeneration	Urban regeneration
Renewable energy for space heating and hot water supply	Integrated renewable energy	Energy efficiency in buildings	Vehicles electric (inc. infrastructures)	Wind power	Urban heating / cooling plant	Waste and wastewater management
Energy efficiency in space heating and hot water supply	Information and communication technologies	Renewable energy	Electric vehicles (inc. Infrastructures)	Photovoltaic energy	Urban heating / cooling network (new installation, extension, refurbishment)	Planting trees in urban areas
Efficient lighting systems	Others	Information and communication technologies	Modal transfer to public transport	Biomass plant	Others	Related to agriculture and forestry
Efficient appliances		Others	Modal transfer to walking and cycling routes	Cogeneration		Others
Integrated action (all of the above)			Car sharing	Smart grids		
Information and communication technologies			Improving logistics operations and urban freight transport	Others		
Habits changes			Optimization of the road network			
Others			Mixed-use urbanization and containment expansion			
			Information and communication technologies			
			Ecological driving			

Table 3-21 Template of the instruments table by sector

<i>tool depending on sector</i>						
Equipment_buildings	Street_lighting	Industry	Transport	Local_electricity_production	Locally_generated_heating_and_cooling	Others
Awareness / training	Energy management	Awareness / training	Awareness / training	Awareness / training	Awareness / training	Awareness / training
Energy management	Obligations of energy suppliers	Energy management	Integration of ticketing and payment systems	Obligations of energy suppliers	Obligations of energy suppliers	Land use planning
Energy certification / labeling	third party financing. Public-private partnerships	Energy certification / labeling	Grants and aid	Grants and aid	Grants and aid	Not applicable
Obligations of energy suppliers	Public procurement	Energy performance standards	Tolls	Third party financing. Public-private partnerships	Third party financing. Public-private partnerships	Others
Taxes on energy / carbon emissions	Not applicable	Taxes on energy / carbon emissions	Territorial planning regulations	Construction requirements	Construction requirements	
Grants and aid	Others	Grants and aid	Transport / mobility planning regulations	Land use planning	Territorial planning regulations	
Third party financing. Public-private partnerships		Third party financing. Public-private partnerships	Public procurement	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Public procurement		Not applicable	Voluntary agreements with the parties involved	Others	Others	
Construction requirements		Others	Not applicable			
Territorial planning regulations			Others			
Not applicable						
Others						

Harmonization of data for the climate change adaptation plan

The harmonization of the climate change adaptation actions, included in the adaptation plan, will consist in a manual mapping between the SECAP Template of the Annex I: SECAP template, and the data model of ePLANET. The ePLANET data model for this use case is organized in several linked tables within a non-structured database (Mongo DB). The templates of the tables corresponding to the actions for adaptation to climate change, are shown in the following tables:

Table 3-22 Template of the input table of adaptation action in ePLANET data model

Hierarchical level 1	Hierarchical level 2	Sectors	Climate risk	USES	Execution status	Affects mitigation
SECTOR	Climate risk	Buildings	Extreme heat	(TO DEFINE)	Not started	0 YES
		Transportation	Extremely cold		In progress	50 NO
		Energy	Extreme rainfall		Completed	100
		Water	Floods			
		Waste	Sea level rise			
		Land Use Planning	Droughts			
		Agriculture and forestry	Storms			
		Environment and biodiversity	Avalanche			
		Health	Forest fires			
		Civil protection and emergencies	Transversal			
		Tourism	Others			
		Others				

Table 3-23 Template of the table for registering each adaptation action

Start date	End date	In charge
2015	2030	Department of the Environment
		Contracting Department
		Department of Education
		Roads and works maintenance departments
		Department of Education and Childhood
		Department of Citizen Participation
		Town planning department
		Town hall
		Commonwealth
		Municipal Brigade

3.2 Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock (UC2)

To make the building energy performance analysis are required building general data and energy consumption data. The general building data indicate the location of the building, the building characteristics like gross floor area, and the climatization source. The energy consumption measurements will reveal the seasonal patterns. The metrics can be calculated to compare the buildings' energy consumption with this information.

The pilots of this use case are the island of Crete and the Zlín Region. Both regions' partners provide the data in Excel files.

3.2.1 Input data format files for Crete region

The electricity consumption from the Crete pilot is provided in Excel files, being one Excel for each municipality. These data come from the energy billing system. Each row contains the information of one electricity bill so that each building will have as many rows as electricity bills. However, not all the bills include new consumption readings, so we will have fewer measurements than rows and the measurement's frequency will not be uniform. For each bill is provided:

- Meter number
- Location:
 - Municipal unit
 - Municipality
 - LAU 2 code
 - Public building name
 - Street name
 - Street number
 - City
- Measurement:
 - Previous accumulated measurement
 - Previous recording date
 - Current accumulated measurement
 - Current recording date
 - Number of days

- Electricity consumption

ΔΗΜΟΣ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ											
ΕΚΔΟΣΕΙΣ 2017											
ΕΤΣ	ΜΗΝ	ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΟΛΛΑΠΛΟΥ	Dimotiki kinotita	ΔΗΜΟΣ	ΚΩΔΙΚΣ ΓΡΑΦΕΙΟΥ	ΟΝΟΜΑ ΓΡΑΦΕΙΟΥ	ΑΡ.ΠΑΡΟΧΗΣ	ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΣ ΣΥΜΒΟΛΑΙΟΥ	ΚΩΔ.Η/ΛΕΚΤ. ΠΛΗΡΩΜΗΣ	ΟΝΟΜΑ ΠΕΛΑΤΗ	ΟΝΟΜΑ ΟΔΟΥ (Περιοχ)
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55457460601	300007393839	554574606014	ΓΥΜΝ.ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55457467202	300007397361	554574672025	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΓΟΡΓΟΛΑΙΝΙ ΔΗΜ ΟΤΙΚ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55457491701	300007414510	554574917017	ΦΟΠ ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55457491801	300007414565	554574918018	ΔΗΜΟΤΙΚΟΝ ΣΧΟΛΕΙΟΝ Μ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55460847501	300007301500	554608475014	ΦΟΠ ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55462053701	300007207161	554620537011	ΑΡΔ.ΚΟΙΝ.ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΑΣ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55462053801	300007207232	554620538010	ΑΡΔ.ΚΟΙΝ.ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΑΣ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55462362601	300007494736	554623626018	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΓΟΡΓΟΛΑΙΝΙ (ΑΝ ΤΑΙΟ	ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΑΣ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55462503501	300007625569	554625035019	ΑΡΔ.ΔΗΜΟΥ ΓΟΡΓΟΛΑΙΝΙ	ΞΕΡΟΛΙΑ-ΑΓ ΜΥΡΩΝΑΣ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55462896601	300008001400	554628966012	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΓΟΡΓΟΛΑΙΝΙ ΦΟΠ	ΑΓ. ΜΥΡΩΝΑ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55463215401	300007066616	554632154010	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΓΟΡΓΟΛΑΙΝΙ ΓΗΠ ΕΔΟ	ΑΓΙΟΣ ΜΥΡΩΝΑΣ
2017	1	Δ008963	ΚΟΙΝ. ΑΓ.ΜΥΡΩΝΟΣ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5100	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	55463718401	300007447170	554637184014	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΓΟΡΓΟΛΑΙΝΙ	ΑΓΙΟΣ ΜΥΡΩΝΑΣ

Figure 3-1 Example Excel from the Heraklion municipality

3.2.2 Input data format files for Zlín region

The public building consumption from the Zlín Region is provided in two types of Excel files. The first type will be a unique Excel file containing the building's general description of all the required public buildings. The second type of data file will be a file for each building containing its energy consumption from different energy sources.

The first data file, which contains the general building information of all the public buildings from the Zlín Region, will have these fields:

- Location:
 - Country
 - Region
 - Municipality
 - Road
 - Road number
 - Postal code
 - Latitude
 - Longitude
- Building identification:
 - Name
 - Use Type
 - Owner
 - Year of construction
- Building characteristics:
 - Area
 - Renewables (Yes/No)
 - Energy audit (Yes/No)
 - Monitoring (Yes/No)
 - Solar PV (Yes/No)
 - PV installed power (kWp)
 - Solar thermal (Yes/No)
 - Solar thermal installed (kW)
- Energy certificate
 - Energy certificate (Yes/No)
 - Energy certificate date

- Energy certificate qualification
- Heating
 - Heating source
 - Original installed power (kW)
 - Installed power after EEM implementation

ePlanet id	Location							Building identification					
Unique Code	Country	Region	Municipality	Road	Road Number	PostalCode	Longitud	Latitud	Name	Use Type	Owner	Year of construction	Gross floor area
eP-EAZK-1	Czech Republic												
eP-EAZK-2	Czech Republic												
eP-EAZK-3	Czech Republic												
eP-EAZK-4	Czech Republic												
eP-EAZK-5	Czech Republic												
eP-EAZK-6	Czech Republic												
eP-EAZK-7	Czech Republic												
eP-EAZK-8	Czech Republic												

Figure 3-2 Excel template for the Zlín Region general building information

There is an energy consumption Excel file for each building. This file will contain the monthly energy consumption disaggregated by source. This file contains this fields:

- Building GPS coordinates
- Monthly natural gas consumption in m³
- Monthly electricity high tariff in kWh
- Monthly electricity low tariff in kWh
- Monthly overall electricity consumption in kWh
- Monthly heat consumption from the district heating system in GJ
- Monthly water consumption in m³

medium	elektrifina celkem	Y	soufadnice	X	Y	GPS		
					497008	1177770 49°7'55.953"N, 18°0'40.831"E		
	rok							
Data	2009		2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Součet z leden	11896		12349	12027	11603	10912	9658	9502
Součet z únor	10524		11243	9994	8458	8608	7617	8941
Součet z březen	8495		11006	11681	9687	9793	8195	7037
Součet z duben	10164		8913	9644	8045	7705	7873	7475
Součet z květen	7653		7467	9423	7678	7367	7634	6969
Součet z červen	6247		7196	6981	6764	6931	6598	6140
Součet z července	2564		3061	3097	3288	3010	3338	3376
Součet z srpen	3239		3732	4172	4359	3825	3782	3675
Součet z září	9291		8428	8824	7713	7464	7909	7067
Součet z říjen	10774		10896	10953	9706	10543	8868	8453
Součet z listopad	11585		11035	11847	10598	10694	9353	8553
Součet z prosinec	10463		10324	9729	9188	8065	7906	7319
Celkem	102895		105650	108372	97087	94917	88731	84507

Figure 3-3 Zlín Region energy consumption Excel example

3.2.3 Data harmonization process

Harmonization of static data of buildings

Static data includes the main features of the buildings (location, building type...). Therefore, the harmonization process mainly focuses on a data mapping of the input files described in the

previous sections and the corresponding data variables of the ePLANET data model for public buildings.

In this use case, the data from the Crete island and the Zlín region public buildings should be harmonized. The data is coming from several excel files. For example, the Zlín region will provide an excel file for each public building. The harmonization process is carried out with a mapping tool to get all this data. First, it is indicated all the data classes that are going to be uploaded from a data source. Then it should be determined which column name refers to each class property.

Figure 3-4 Screenshot from the harmonization application

Using this tool will enable us to upload all the building information provided by the pilots to the ePLANET database already harmonized.

The data flow inside the mapping tool is to generate a mapping file based on YARRML. This file is then used to parse it into RML or R2RML rules, which are standard languages understood by many tools that provide tabular data for RDF transformation. Both transformations, from YARRML to RML/R2RML and from the tabular input data to RDF driven by the resulting RML/R2RML rules, are implemented using two docker containers.

Figure 3-5 Internal mapping tool workflow

The final data is stored in RDF (Resource Description Framework) which is the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) standard for data exchange on the Web. The model used to represent the data is a directed graph. The graph is stored using a structure of triplets. The idea of a triplet is simple. It consists of logical assertions of the form subject, predicate and object, where each triplet expresses a specific fact about a subject. Finally, when the triplets are linked, it forms a graph.

Harmonization of time series data (monthly energy consumption)

In ePLANET data model classes and attributes related to time series data are represented as columns. A colour code indicates obligatory, desired and optional mapping fields. For a timeseries data input to be successfully mapped, red coloured attributes (columns) should be filled, yellow columns are desired and white ones are optional.

Each time series input, filled by rows, should be implicitly or explicitly mapped following the previously described colour keys. If enumeration type input attributes have their counterpart in the ePLANET data model they are considered as explicit and should be mapped using its attribute source name. On the other hand, implicit mapping occurs when there are input attributes that include information regarding other attributes implicitly. For instance, units are common to be implicit within time series data given that the property measured has a commonly known/used unit of measurement, or when data providers know it without putting it explicitly. If the field in discussion is implicit and of an enumeration type, it should be filled according to its taxonomy sheet using quotation marks.

	A	B	C	D	M	S	T	U	V	AA	
1				Time series mapping							
2				Class name							
3				Device		Measurement			MeasurementList		
4				deviceID	deviceType	measurementEnd	measurementStart	measurementValue	measuredProperty	measurementUnit	
5				Unique identifier for the device	Type of the device	Final timestamp of the reference period associated with the measurement	Initial timestamp of the reference period associated with the measurement	Value of the property measured by the device	Physical property measured by the device	Unit of measurement of the property values	
6				Source class	UID	enum	datetime	datetime	any	enum	
7											
8											
9	1	hourly_consumption	cups	"SmartMeter"	datetime			consumptionKWh	"Energy_ConsumptionGridElectricity"	"kWh"	
10	2	quarter_hourly_consumption	cups	"SmartMeter"	datetime			consumptionKWh	"Energy_ConsumptionGridElectricity"	"kWh"	
11	3										
12	4										
13	5										
14	6										
15	7										
16	8										
17	9										
18	10										
19	11										
20	12										
21	13										
22	14										
23	15										
24											

Figure 3-6 Example table of time series data in the ePLANET data model

3.3 Geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities (UC3)

Promoting Renewable Energy Communities (REC) and Citizen Energy Communities (CEC) is a relatively new target at the municipal level. Due to this situation, each pilot region is in different stages of this promotion, so they have different needs.

For this, the data provided by each pilot region is different.

3.3.1 Common input data files

This use case comprises the geo reference analysis of several entities, ranging from individual buildings (Girona region) to municipalities (Crete region). The Eurostat NUTS and LAUs standards are adopted to have all this uneven data stored in the same data model. This standard is a geocode for statistical purposes referencing the administrative subdivisions of the European countries.

These harmonized NUTS and LAUs with their corresponding geo file, can be download in:

- <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/lau#lau19>
- <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/nuts#nuts21>

3.3.2 Input data format files for Crete region

RES installations

In this case, the need is to have a geo referenced visualization of all the RES installations at the municipal level with its generation capacity. For this purpose, the project partner from Crete provides an Excel file with the RES installations from the Crete island. This file contains:

- Plant code
- Technology (photovoltaic, hydroelectric, biogas or wind farm)
- Type of grid connection (medium voltage or low voltage)
- Location
- Municipality
- Municipal unit
- Province
- Installed power

ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑ	ΣΥΝΔΕΣΗ ΣΤΟ ΔΙΚΤΥΟ	Όψη εγκατάστασης Σταθμού ΑΠΕ (τοποθεσία)	Νησί	Δήμος	Δημοτική Κοινότητα	Νομός	Τελική Ρυθμιζόμενη Ισχύς (kW)
ΑΠ - Αιολικό Πάρκο	M.T.	ΜΕΓΑΛΗ ΘΡΥΣΗ ΔΗΜΟΥ ΓΟΡΤΥΝΑΣ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΑΓ. ΒΑΡΒΑΡΑΣ)	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΓΟΡΤΥΝΑΣ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΑΓ. ΒΑΡΒΑΡΑΣ)		ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	4950
ΑΠ - Αιολικό Πάρκο	M.T.	ΒΟΣΚΕΡΟ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΜΑΛΕΒΙΖΙΟΥ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΚΡΟΥΣΩΝΑ)	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΜΑΛΕΒΙΖΙΟΥ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΚΡΟΥΣΩΝΑ)		ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5950
ΑΠ - Αιολικό Πάρκο	M.T.	ΠΕΡΔΙΚΟΚΟΥΡΥΦΗ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΓΟΡΤΥΝΑΣ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΑΓ. ΒΑΡΒΑΡΑΣ)	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΓΟΡΤΥΝΑΣ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΑΓ. ΒΑΡΒΑΡΑΣ)		ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	14450
ΑΠ - Αιολικό Πάρκο	M.T.	ΑΝΤΙΚΑΡΙ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΦΑΙΣΤΟΥ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΜΟΙΡΩΝ)	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΦΑΙΣΤΟΥ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΜΟΙΡΩΝ)		ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5250
ΑΠ - Αιολικό Πάρκο	M.T.	ΑΓΙΟΣ ΚΥΡΥΛΛΟΣ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΓΟΡΤΥΝΑΣ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΥ ΓΟΡΤΥΝΑΣ		ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	7200
ΑΠ - Αιολικό Πάρκο	M.T.	ΚΑΛΟΓΗΡΟΣ ΔΗΜΟΥ ΜΑΛΕΒΙΖΙΟΥ (ΠΡΩΗΝ ΓΑΖΙΟΥ)	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΜΑΛΕΒΙΖΙΟΥ	ΚΟΙΝ. ΓΑΖΙΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	3600
ΑΠ - Αιολικό Πάρκο	M.T.	ΕΠΑΝΩΣΗΦΗΣ ΔΗΜΟΥ ΚΑΖΑΝΤΖΑΚΗ - ΤΕΜΕΝΟΥΣ Ν. ΠΕΡΑΧΩΝ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΑΡΧΑΝΩΝ-ΑΣΤΕΡΟΥΣΙΩΝ		ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	5950
ΒΙΟΑ - Βιοαέριο	M.T.	ΣΥΜΒΟΛΗ ΟΔΩΝ Α & Π Ο.Τ. 3 ΒΙ. ΠΕ. ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ		ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	999
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	M.T.	ΛΙΜΕΝΑΣ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ ΔΗΜΟΥ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΧΕΡΣΙΟΝΗΣΟΥ	ΚΟΙΝ. Λ.ΧΕΡΣΙΟΝΗΣΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	19.955
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	M.T.	ΜΕΣΟΧΩΡΙΟ, ΔΗΜΟΣ ΑΡΧΑΝΩΝ-ΑΣΤΕΡΟΥΣΙΩΝ (ΠΡΩ. ΜΕΣΟΧΩΡΙΟΥ)	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΑΡΧΑΝΩΝ-ΑΣΤΕΡΟΥΣΙΩΝ	ΚΟΙΝ. ΜΕΣΟΧΩΡΙΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	168.84
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	M.T.	ΒΙΠΕ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ	ΔΗΜΟΣ Ν.ΑΛΙΚΑΡΝΑΣΣΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	126.7
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	X.T.	ΑΡΧ. ΜΑΚΑΡΙΟΥ 36, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	4.84
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	X.T.	ΕΠΙ ΚΤΗΡΙΟΥ "BOWLING CENTER", ΛΕΩΦ. ΙΚΑΡΟΥ & ΕΥΡΩΠΗΣ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	20
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	X.T.	ΞΕΡΟΚΑΜΠΟΣ, Δ.Δ. ΒΑΧΟΥ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΟΙΝ. ΒΑΧΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	79.2
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	X.T.	ΛΕΙΒΑΔΑΚΙΑ, Δ.Δ. ΒΑΧΟΥ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΟΙΝ. ΒΑΧΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	79.2
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	X.T.	ΣΚΛΑΒΕΡΟΥ, Δ.Δ. ΒΑΧΟΥ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΟΙΝ. ΒΑΧΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	79.56
Φ/Β - Φωτοβολταϊκό	X.T.	ΞΕΡΟΚΑΜΠΟΣ, Δ.Δ. ΒΑΧΟΥ, ΔΗΜΟΥ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΡΗΤΗ	ΔΗΜΟΣ ΒΙΑΝΝΟΥ	ΚΟΙΝ. ΒΑΧΟΥ	ΗΡΑΚΛΕΙΟΥ	79.2

Figure 3-7 Crete island, RES installation Excel file

Energy consumption of municipality split by sector

An excel file will provide the electrical energy demand by municipality following the same scheme as the RES installations case. The difference between both cases is that instead of having the RES technology, it will indicate the sector that consumes the energy. The different aggregated sectors are:

- Residential
- Public buildings
- Public lighting
- Water management
- Agriculture
- Trade
- Industry

Geo referenced electricity consumption of public buildings

The provided data is in the same format as the data provided in the UC2. Therefore, is used the same harmonization process to upload the data to the ePLANET platform. The buildings are linked to the municipality by the LAU code and are also geo referenced.

3.3.3 Input data format files for Girona region

Electricity and gas consumption of each building block from the Spanish DSOs

In Girona region, a geo referenced tool is required to detect potential energy communities. Due to the maximum 500 meters between the PV and the community members set by the Spanish regulation, the electric consumption and generation should be geo referenced. In this way, it could be considered the distance between the community members and the PV installation in the design process of the energy community. Also, detecting the points of high heating demand should be helpful in deciding where to boost energy communities with biomass boilers. The implementation of this use case will cover 67 municipalities; however, the harmonization process will be divided into two stages:

1. Stage 1: 6 municipalities:
 - a. Campdevanol: INE municipal code: 170366
 - b. Cassà de la Selva: INE municipal code: 170448
 - c. Palafrugell: INE municipal code: 171175
 - d. Ripoll: INE municipal code: 171479
 - e. Sant Feliu de Guixols: INE municipal code: 171609
 - f. Sarria de Ter: INE municipal code: 171864.
2. Stage 2: The remaining 61 municipalities

For this use case, the electricity and gas consumption data are provided by the distribution system operators (e-Distribución and NEDGIA). These data sets have been already gathered by CIMNE and include historical data for the last 3 years in monthly frequency in the case of the electricity consumption data and in yearly frequency in the case of the gas consumption. Following the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and to guarantee user privacy, the monthly electricity consumption data are aggregated at the building level, with a lower threshold of 4 different supply connections. The data obtained includes these fields:

- Postal code
- Municipality
- Street name and street number
- Monthly energy consumption (gas or electricity)

The electricity consumption data will be enhanced with detailed open data which is available (through a public API) in the web portal of the Spanish distributor operators, DATADIS (<https://datadis.es/en>). These data sets include aggregated hourly electricity consumption, disaggregated by tariffs and economic sector, on a postal code level provided. The fields provided by this data source are:

- Day
- Month
- Year
- Postal code
- Fare
- Time discrimination

- Daily consumption
- Number of supply points aggregated
- Economic sector
- Supplied tension
- Hourly consumption

dataDay	dataMonth	dataYear	community	postalCode	fare	timeDiscrimination	sumEnergy	sumContracts	tension	economicSector	mi1	mi2	mi3	mi4	mi5
0	1	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	604	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	18	16	15	14	13
1	2	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	659	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	25	19	16	16	11
2	3	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	603	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	22	21	15	16	13
3	4	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	630	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	18	19	15	15	13
4	5	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	670	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	23	19	18	19	14
5	6	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	707	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	24	24	22	20	23
6	7	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	688	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	24	25	20	20	16
7	8	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	682	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	22	22	19	16	16
8	9	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	719	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	27	22	20	16	17
9	10	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	687	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	24	22	21	16	15
10	11	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	626	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	22	21	18	17	17
11	12	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	630	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	21	19	13	15	14
12	13	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	614	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	18	16	15	14	13
13	14	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	599	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	24	22	21	19	26
14	15	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	677	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	20	18	17	16	16
15	16	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	682	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	22	21	19	16	22
16	17	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	637	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	16	19	16	15	20
17	18	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	632	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	16	16	15	14	19
18	19	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	594	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	19	18	14	16	16
19	20	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	629	42 E0	RESIDENCIAL	16	16	15	15	19
20	21	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	693	43 E0	RESIDENCIAL	17	17	15	15	21
21	22	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	801	43 E0	RESIDENCIAL	23	20	18	18	16
22	23	6	2019	Cataluña	17124	GENERAL BAJA TENSIÓN, POTENCIA NO SUPERIOR A 10 kW	TARIFA DE DOS PERIODOS	850	43 E0	RESIDENCIAL	34	27	23	21	27

Figure 3-8 Girona region, DATADIS data sample

Since the gas consumption is provided at annual basis and at building level, there is no need to limit the dataset to the buildings with more than 4 supply connections. The fields obtained from the gas consumption are:

- Location:
 - Province
 - City
 - Street
 - Number
 - Municipality
- Number of supply connections
- Yearly consumption

FINCA	MUNICIPI	Vol PS	Consum 2018	Consum 2019	Consum 2020	Consum 2021
GIRONA@AGULLANA@GERMANS_ESCOLES_CRISTIANES@6@	AGULLANA	4	997	987	892	1.015
GIRONA@AGULLANA@GERMANS_ESCOLES_CRISTIANES@8@	AGULLANA	6	1.473	1.852	1.280	1.253
GIRONA@AGULLANA@PONENT@21@	AGULLANA	4	541	479	441	447
GIRONA@ALP@AGNES_FABRA@0018@A	ALP	11	1.687	2.013	1.585	1.672
GIRONA@ALP@AGNES_FABRA@0018@B	ALP	7	1.827	1.952	1.814	1.768
GIRONA@ALP@ALP_A_LA_MOLINA@005N@	ALP	8	4.229	3.545	2.845	2.646
GIRONA@ALP@ARRABAL@0001@	ALP	5	1.169	1.072	681	926

Figure 3-9 Girona province, data sample of the monthly gas consumption

The datasets provided by the Spanish DSO do not contain any geo reference, therefore the cadastral data (which is already harmonized following the INSPIRE directive³) will be used to assign the corresponding geo reference to each building. The cadastral data include:

- X coordinate
- Y coordinate
- Cadastral reference
- Address
- Municipality
- Year of construction

³ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/inspire-directive/2>

- Gross floor area

The process to merge the data sets from the DSO and the geo referenced data from the cadastral is performed within the data harmonization procedure and it is further explained in detail.

PV potential of all rooftops from GIS layer

The PV solar potential, at rooftop level, is obtained from a detailed analysis of the solar PV power potential of the rooftops of all the municipalities of the Girona provinces, which was contracted by DDGI to the consultancy company Anthesis Labola. This detailed analysis can be found in the web of DDGI (https://www.ddgi.cat/ddgi/docNivell/medi_ambient/pacte_alcaldes/00_ESTUDI_POTENCIAL_SOLAR.pdf). It is also published in shape file format, in the Municipal System of Territorial Information (SITMUN) of the Girona province (<https://sitmun.ddgi.cat/sitmun/visor-ddgi.jsp?app=1&ter=1&lang=ca>). This GIS based system provides the potential PV power and the estimated annual solar energy generation of each rooftop.

Figure 3-10 Girona province, SITMUN photovoltaic potential visualization

Electricity and gas consumption of public buildings and public lighting from energy accounting services

The Girona pilot municipalities have already centralized their energy consumption data into energy management platforms. Some of them use Gemweb and others use the SIE platform from Inergy. A communication API will be used to get the public building data from these platforms. Then, it is going to be used the same approach as the UC2; the harmonized data will be uploaded to the ePLANET platform using the presented harmonization software.

3.3.4 Input data format files for Zlín region

The application of this use case in Zlín region consists of an existing energy community corresponding to all the Hostětín village. In this use case, the data is provided in the same format as the data from the UC2. This data already contains the GPS coordinates, so they are already geo referenced. Therefore, the harmonisation identification is the same.

3.3.5 Data harmonization process

Harmonisation of data from Crete Island

In this use case is received two different Excel files as input data from Crete's pilot. The first one is the RES installations data which is mapped using the developed mapping tool. The data model used is the same as the one used by the static data of buildings. However, in the data model it is included specifically for this case, the technology field in order to indicate the RES energy type.

The second file input is the municipal energy consumption split by sector. In this case, is also used the same data model setting the building class as the municipality and each sector as a building space.

Harmonisation of data from Girona region

Regarding the data coming from the electricity and gas DSO, the following data sets were gathered:

- Monthly electricity consumption of the buildings aggregated at least in 4 end supply points (January 2018 - December 2020);
- Yearly gas consumption of each building (January 2018 - December 2020);
- Cadastral data (sets of coordinates, economic sector, total surface);
- Aggregated hourly electricity consumption on a postal code level (January 2018 - December 2020);

In order to merge all these different datasets, some data transformations are required to achieve a structure that is common for all of them:

- Transformation of monthly Electricity Consumption data: The columns which are not relevant for further work (time period, number of clients, type of the street) were deleted. The column names were translated to English, and rows without values were deleted (number of clients ≤ 4). An additional column was created to include the code of the municipalities (INE code). To facilitate the data files merge, the dataset was split into smaller datasets containing information of only one municipality. The street and number columns were combined in a single column to facilitate the merging.
- Transformation of yearly gas consumption data: The column with addresses was split into a few columns based on the @ separator (province, municipality, street, number). Columns that were not relevant were deleted, and the column with the municipality code was added. Next, some strings were replaced ('_' \rightarrow ' ') to have the same format as in other datasets.

Data sets of the DSO and the cadastral ones (which include the geo reference of each building) will be merged using a fuzzy merge. Fuzzy merge is a smart data preparation feature you can use to apply fuzzy matching algorithms when comparing columns, to try to find matches across the tables that are being merged. The function was downloaded from the fuzzywuzzy Python library⁴, which helps match addresses between one dataset and another. In the case of ePLANET, the fuzzy joint was done between electricity/gas consumption and the cadastral data for each postal code. Some test code runs were performed to define the best threshold for the merge. The order of the variables inside the function matters. Therefore, cadastral data were placed before the electricity consumption to avoid losing some important information. The

⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/fuzzywuzzy/>

column used to compare was the one named 'ADDRESS' because it contains both the name of the street and the number.

The output files, once the data merge is performed, contain the hourly electricity consumption profile, the monthly electricity and gas consumption, the cadastral reference, the LAU 2 code to which each building belongs to, and some geometric features of each individual building (roof area, number of floors...). This information will be then used in the data analytics processing and in the connection with the geo referenced visualization tools, such as the SITMUN platform.

Harmonisation of data from Zlín region

The data represented on the GIS application from the Zlín region pilot is the buildings consumption from Hostětín town, given by an Excel file with the same structure as the ones provided in the UC2. Therefore, the harmonization process is the same as in the UC2.

3.4 PV potential analysis for public buildings (UC4)

The UC4 consists on determining the PV availability on public building rooftops. The only pilot of this use case is the Zlín Region.

3.4.1 Input data format files for Zlín region

LIDAR data files

The data provided is a cloud of points indicating the rooftops scan. This data contains the geo reference in the Coordinate Reference System (CRS) EPSG:5514 - S-JTSK/ Krovak East North and the height of the scan. These points will be processed in order to detect the building's covers and then determine the roof tilt and its shadows. With this data, it can be estimated the possible energy generation.

Figure 3-11 Zlín Region, LIDAR rooftops scan visualization

Cadaster data files

For the roof detection are used the LIDAR data and the building shape from the Czech cadastral data. The cadastral data can be found at:

- <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets?locale=en&catalog=cuzk&page=2&sort=modified%2Bdesc,%20relevance%2Bdesc,%20title.en%2Basc>

3.4.2 Data harmonization process

LIDAR files are not changed during the harmonization process since they are referenced in standard coordinates.

Cadaster data files are neither modified in the harmonization since they are already standard following INSPIRE data format.

4 Annex I: SECAP template

In this annex are presented screenshots of the SECAP template provided by the Covenant of Mayors. This template is used by the local authorities to calculate their CO₂ emissions and assess their action plans.

Strategy HOME

1) Long-term vision (e.g. 2100, not beyond): 1000 chars left

2) Target(s) and commitment(s)

CO ₂ GHG Target	Unit	Target Year	Mitigation		Exposition estimates in target year
			Base Year	Type	
	%	2020	[drop-down]	[drop-down]	
	%	2030	[drop-down]	[drop-down]	
	%	2050	[drop-down]	[drop-down]	

Ⓞ Only if your local authority has set up a 2020 objective. Ⓞ Only if your local authority has set up a 2030 objective.

Ⓞ Add as many rows as necessary.

Adaptation				
Goal	Unit	Target year	Base Year	Progress towards target
	[drop-down]	[drop-down]	[drop-down]	
	[drop-down]	[drop-down]	[drop-down]	

Ⓞ Only if your local authority is committed to adaptation. # Add as many rows as necessary.

3) Administrative structure

Type of administrative structure

- Mono-sectorial - one officer or one sectorial department assigned within the municipal
- Multi-sectorial - several departments assigned within the municipal administration
- Multi-level - several departments assigned at different level(s) of governance (e.g.

Comments [v] Ⓞ Click on the [+/-] button on the left to expand or collapse. 1000 chars left

4) Staff capacity allocated

Type	Plan preparation			Plan implementation		
	Mitigation	Adaptation	(Estimated) full-time equivalent job(s)	Mitigation	Adaptation	(Estimated) full-time equivalent job(s)
Local authority	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Other level(s) of governance (e.g. Covenant coordinator or supporter)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
External consultant	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Other	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Total			0			0

Comments [v] Ⓞ Click on the [+/-] button on the left to expand or collapse. 1000 chars left

5) Stakeholder engagement

Type of stakeholders	Stakeholders engaged	Engagement level	Engagement method(s)	Engagement purpose
Local authority's staff	<input type="checkbox"/>	[drop-down]	Workshop; Focus group; Citizen jury; Other	Consultation; Advice; Co-production; Co-decision; Implementation
External stakeholders at local level	<input type="checkbox"/>	[drop-down]	Workshop; Focus group; Citizen jury; Other	Consultation; Advice; Co-production; Co-decision; Implementation
Stakeholders at other levels of governance	<input type="checkbox"/>	[drop-down]	Workshop; Focus group; Citizen jury; Other	Consultation; Advice; Co-production; Co-decision; Implementation

Ⓞ Select x for the ones that are applicable. Ⓞ Delete categories that are not applicable. Ⓞ Delete categories that are not applicable. Ⓞ Delete categories that are not applicable.

Comments [v] Ⓞ Click on the [+/-] button on the left to expand or collapse. 700 chars left

6) Budget

Overall budget foreseen for plan implementation		Budget spent so far	
Total (€)	Mitigation (%)	Total (€)	Mitigation (%)

Ⓞ % to be reported only for signatories also committed to

Budget period: From: 2012 To: 2030 Ⓞ depending on signatories' selected time horizon (2020/2020)

Financing sources		Share (in % of overall)
Local Authority's own resources	<input type="checkbox"/>	
External sources	<input type="checkbox"/>	
-> Public	<input type="checkbox"/>	
-> Private	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Not allocated to any sources	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Comments [v] Ⓞ Click on the [+/-] button on the left to expand or collapse. 700 chars left

7) Monitoring process 1000 chars left

HOME

Emission Inventory

To be filled in only if your local authority is committed to mitigation.
 Copy as many "emission inventory" tabs as necessary. Minimum 1 "baseline emission inventory" (BE) at the 1st reporting stage, minimum 1 "monitoring emission inventory" (ME) every 4 years.

1 Inventory year:

2 Population in the inventory year:

3 Emission factors: IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) National/sub-national Specify: Source:

4 Emission reporting unit: tonnes CO₂ tonnes CO₂ equivalent

5 Methodological note:

A. Final energy consumption

Please note that for separating decimals dot (.) is used. No thousand separators are allowed.
 Please note that the following notation keys can be used in the table below: "N" (not occurring), "IE" (included elsewhere), "NE" (not estimated) and "C" (confidential). More information in the Reporting Guidelines.
 Click on the [+/-] buttons on the left to expand or collapse. Hide rows as appropriate to your emission inventory.

Sector	FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION (MWh)											Renewable energies					Total
	Electricity	District heating and	Natural gas	Liquid gas	Heating oil	Diesel	Gasoline	Lignite	Coal	Other fossil fuels	Biogas	Plant oil	Biofuel	Other biomass	Solar thermal	Geothermal	
BUILDINGS, EQUIPMENT/FACILITIES	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Municipal buildings, equipment/facilities	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Municipal buildings, equipment/facilities	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Public lighting	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Other	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Tertiary (non-municipal) buildings	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Tertiary (non-municipal) buildings	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Tertiary (non-municipal) buildings	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Tertiary (non-municipal) buildings	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Residential buildings	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Industry	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Industry	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Buildings, equipment/facilities and	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Buildings, equipment/facilities and	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
TRANSPORT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Municipal fleet	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Road	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Other	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Public transport	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Public transport	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Road	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Rail	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Local and domestic water	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Other	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Private and commercial transport	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Private and commercial transport	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Road	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Rail	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Local and domestic water	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Local aviation	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Other	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Transport not allocated	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Transport not allocated	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
OTHER	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
Other not allocated	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	
TOTAL	#VALORI	#VALORI	#VALORI	#VALORI	#VALORI	#VALORI	###	#VALORI	####	#VALORI	#####	#####	#####	#####	#VALORI	#VALORI	

Covenant Key Sectors

B. Energy supply

Hide sections or rows as appropriate to your emission inventory.

B1. Certified green electricity

Certified green electricity	Renewable electricity (MWh)	CO ₂ / CO ₂ eq. emission
Purchases, Guarantees of Origin, Guarantees of Origin (within the municipality boundaries)	NE	NE

B2. Local distributed electricity production (Renewable energy only)

Local renewable electricity plants	Renewable electricity produced (MWh)	Emission factor (t/MWh)	CO ₂ / CO ₂ eq.
Wind	NE	#VALORI	#VALORI
Hydroelectric	NE	#VALORI	#VALORI
Photovoltaics	NE	#VALORI	#VALORI
Geothermal	NE	#VALORI	#VALORI
Other	NE	#VALORI	#VALORI
TOTAL	0	#VALORI	#VALORI

B3. Local distributed electricity production

Local electricity production plants	Electricity produced (MWh)		Energy carrier input (MWh)										CO ₂ / CO ₂ eq.		
	from renewable sources	from non-renewable	Natural gas	Liquid gas	Heating oil	Lignite	Coal	Waste	Plant oil	Other biomass	Biogas	Other renew	Other	Fossil sources	Renewable sources
Combined Heat and Power	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
Other (ETS and large-scale plants)	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
TOTAL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

B4. Local heat/cold production

Local heat/cold production plants	Heat/cold produced (MWh)		Energy carrier input (MWh)										CO ₂ / CO ₂ eq.		
	from renewable sources	from non-renewable	Natural gas	Liquid gas	Heating oil	Lignite	Coal	Waste	Plant oil	Other biomass	Biogas	Other renew	Other	Fossil sources	Renewable sources
Combined Heat and Power	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
District heating (heat-only)	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
Other	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
TOTAL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

C. CO₂ emissions

C1. Please insert the CO₂ emission factors adopted [t/MWh]:

Click here to visualise fuel emission factors

National	Local	Heat/cold	Emission factors													
			Natural gas	Liquid gas	Heating oil	Diesel	Gasoline	Lignite	Coal	Other fossil fuels	Biogas	Plant oil	Other biomass	Solar thermal	Geothermal	

C2. Please complete in case non-energy related sectors are included:

Click on the [+/-] buttons on the left to expand or collapse.

Non-energy related sectors	CO ₂ eq. emissions (t)	Activity data (tons)
Waste management	0	0
Solid waste disposal	NE	NE
Biological Treatment of Incineration and Open B	NE	NE
Other	NE	NE
Wastewater treatment and discharge	NE	NE
Other non-energy related such as fuel	NE	NE

Emission Inventory Summary

The emission inventory summary table is automatically generated in the online platform (MyCovenant).

Additional comments:

500 chars left

HOME

Risk & Vulnerability Assessment (RVA)

Note that the online platform MyCovenant applies an IT solution through which tables in the RVA are generated automatically and prefilled depending on previously made selections.

While content in this file and in MyCovenant is the same, the method of completion of the RVA will slightly differ.

Underlined words are defined; definitions are visible upon clicking the respective cell. Definitions of climate hazards,
 ☐ To choose option(s) from a predefined list, copy and paste the relevant option(s). 'Single choice' indicates only one

Table 1) Climate hazards

Climate hazards	Current risk of hazard occurring			<< Future hazards >>	
	Probability of hazard	Impact of hazard	Expected change in hazard	Expected change in hazard	Timeframes
	Single choice: Low Moderate High Not known	Single choice: Low Moderate High Not known	Single choice: Increase Decrease No change Not known	Single choice: Increase Decrease No change Not known	Multiple choice: Short-term Mid-term Long-term Not known
☐ Extreme heat	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Extreme cold	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Heavy precipitation	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Heavy rainfall	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Heavy snowfall	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Fog	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Hail	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Floods & sea level rise	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Flash / surface flood	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
River flood	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Coastal flood	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Groundwater flood	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Permanent inundation	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Droughts & water scarcity	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Storms	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Severe wind	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Tornado	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Cyclone (hurricane / typhoon)	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Tropical storm	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Extratropical storm	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Storm surge	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Lightning / thunderstorm	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Mass movement	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Landslide	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Avalanche	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Rockfall	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Subsidence	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Wild fires	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Forest fire	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Land fire	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Chemical change	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Saltwater intrusion	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Ocean acidification	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Atmospheric CO2	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Biological hazards	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Water-borne disease	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Vector-borne disease	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Airborne disease	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
Insect infestation	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]
☐ Other	[Please specify]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]	[Please choose]

☐ Step 1) Check the boxes for the climate hazards that are applicable to your local authority >>> Step 2) Fill in all green fields for the selected hazards by choosing (i.e. copying and pasting) option(s) in row# 14 >>> Step 3) Optionally, fill in information for the relevant sub-hazards (do not fill anything for sub-hazards that are not relevant).

Table 2) Vulnerable sectors

Climate hazards	Relevant vulnerable	Current vulnerability	Indicator
	Multiple choice: Buildings Transport Energy Water Waste Land use planning & Agriculture &	Single choice: Low Moderate High Not known	Choose an indicator from Annex 3, Table 1, along with a unit and numeric value, or write down your own indicator.
☐ Extreme heat	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Extreme cold	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Heavy precipitation	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Floods & sea level rise	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Droughts & water scarcity	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Storms	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Mass movement	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Wild fires	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Other	[Please specify]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]

☐ Specify your indicators in Annex 3, Table 1 (optional)

Table 3) Adaptive capacity

Impacted sector(s)	Relevant climate hazards	Adaptive capacity	Current	Indicator
	☐ Column not to be filled in	Multiple choice: Access to	Single choice: Low	Choose an indicator from Annex 3, Table 1, along with a unit and numeric value, or write down your own.
☐ Buildings	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Transport	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Energy	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Water	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Waste	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Land use planning	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Agriculture & forestry	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Environment & biodiversity	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Health	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Civil protection & emergency	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Tourism	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ Education	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]
☐ ICT (Information & communication)	[to be generated automatically in the list]	[Choose from the list]	[Please choose]	[Choose from Annex 3 or write down your own]

☐ Specify your indicators in Annex 3, Table 2 (optional)

Table 4) Vulnerable population groups

Climate hazards	Most vulnerable population group(s)
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Step 8) Mark again with a tick box the same hazards selected in Table 1 above (in the online template, these hazards will be generated/displayed automatically). Ignore the rest of the hazards. >>> Step 9) Choose (i.e. copy-paste) the most vulnerable population</p>	
<p>Multiple choice:</p> <p>Women and girls Children Youth Elderly Marginalized groups</p>	
<input type="checkbox"/> Extreme heat	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Extreme cold	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Heavy precipitation	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Floods & sea level rise	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Droughts & water scarcity	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Storms	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Mass movement	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Wild fires	Choose from the
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	please

Additional comments

Action Plan HOME

1 Action plan(s) and other related documents

1 Action plan(s)

Title	Short description	Date of formal approval	Decision body approving the plan	Nature of the document	Scope / Boundary	Language	Published?
		dd/mm/yy dd/mm/yy					<input type="checkbox"/>

2 Other related documents

Add additional rows as necessary

Title	Short description	Date	Author(s)	Nature of the document	Scope / Boundary	Method &	Language	Published
		dd/mm/yy dd/mm/yy						<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments [v] Click on the [+/-] button on the left to expand or collapse.

List of actions

Please specify the total number of (mitigation and adaptation) actions planned per sector. For mitigation actions, estimate their impacts in your plan's time horizon (2020, 2030 and/or other).

3 Mitigation actions

Only if your local authority is committed to mitigation.

Mitigation sectors	Number of actions included in the plan
Municipal buildings, equipment/facilities	
Tertiary (non municipal) buildings	
Residential buildings	
Industry	
Transport	
Waste	
Local Electricity Production	
Local Heat/Cold Production	
Others	
TOTAL	

Action plan implementation status				MONITORING		
Completed (%)	On-going (%)	Postponed (%)	Not-started (%)	Estimated impacts in relation to:		
				BEI		
				Energy/Renewab	CO ₂	
				MWh/a	MWh/a	t CO ₂ a
				0	0	0

4 Adaptation actions

Only if your local authority is committed to adaptation.

Adaptation sectors	Number of actions included in the plan
Buildings	
Transport	
Energy	
Water	
Waste	
Land Use Planning	
Agriculture & Forestry	
Environment & Biodiversity	
Health	
Civil Protection & Emergency	
Tourism	
Education	
ICT (Information & communication technologies)	
Other	
TOTAL	

Action plan implementation status				MONITORING		
Completed (%)	On-going (%)	Postponed (%)	Not-started (%)	Estimated impacts in relation to:		
				BEI		
				Energy/Renewab	CO ₂	
				MWh/a	MWh/a	t CO ₂ a
				0	0	0

Actions
HOME

Actions

① Copy as many "action" tabs as necessary (**minimum 3 mitigation actions and 3 adaptation actions**)
 ① For the actions your local authority considered as "key actions" - fill in the dedicated "key action" tab.

1) Type of action

Mitigation
 Adaptation
 Energy poverty ① Only in combination with 'Mitigation' and/or 'Adaptation' actions

2) Title of the action

3) Origin of the action

4) Responsible body

5) Short description 1000 characters left

6) Implementation timeframe

Start:
 End:

7) Implementation status

8) Stakeholders involved ① For multiple choice, insert additional rows as needed

Additional comments

9) Total implementation costs: €

Source of funding: €

Investment costs: €

Non-investment costs: €

A. Mitigation

① Only for actions addressing mitigation. Click on the [+/-] buttons on the left to ex

10 Sector

	Buildings	Public lighting	Transport	Industry	Electricity Production	Heat/cold Production	Other	
Tool / Area of intervention:	<input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="drop-down"/>							
Policy instrument:	<input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="drop-down"/>							

① To be filled in only for the concerned sector

11 Estimated impacts

Energy	<input style="width: 80px;" type="text"/>	MWh/a
Renewable	<input style="width: 80px;" type="text"/>	MWh/a
CO ₂ reduction:	<input style="width: 80px;" type="text"/>	t CO ₂ /a

12 Vulnerable population groups ① For multiple choice, insert additional rows as needed

13 Financial savings €

14 Life expectancy of the action years

15 Return on Investment %

16 Jobs created full-time equivalent

17 Other figures merial va [Unit]

B. Adaptation
 ⓘ Only for actions addressing adaptation. Click on the [+/-] buttons on the left to e

18 Climate hazard(s) address: ⓘ For multiple choice, insert additional rows as needed

19 Sector(s) ⓘ For multiple choice, insert additional rows as needed

20 Outcome(s) reached
 Description: 1000 characters left
 Related indicator:

21 Vulnerable population gr ⓘ For multiple choice, insert additional rows as needed

22 Avoided cost €

23 Life expectancy of the action years

24 Return on Investment %

25 Jobs created full-time equivalent

26 Other figures

C. Energy poverty
 ⓘ Only for actions addressing energy poverty. Click on the [+/-] buttons on the left

27 Vulnerable population gr ⓘ For multiple choice, insert additional rows as needed

28 Outcome(s) reached
 Description: 1000 characters left
 Related indicator:

Further information

30 Weblink

31 Video link

32 Picture